

**ВЛИЯНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА НА
ЮРИДИЧЕСКУЮ ПРАКТИКУ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ И ПРАВОВОЕ
ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ**

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены понятие искусственного интеллекта и сфера его применения в юридической практике, международный опыт использования искусственного интеллекта, проблемы, возникающие в результате использования искусственного интеллекта, а также ряд предложений по их решению.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект (ИИ), машинное обучение (МО), чат-боты, юридическое прогнозирование, юридические исследования.

**YURIDIK AMALIYOTDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT
TEKNOLOGIYALARINING TA'SIRI: NAZARIY-HUQUQIY TADQIQOT
ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt tushunchasi hamda uning yuridik amaliyotda qo'llanilish doirasi, sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish bo'yicha xalqaro tajriba, sun'iy intellektning qo'llanilishi natijasida vujudga keldigan muammolar hamda ularga yechim sifatida bir nechta takliflar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sun'iy intellekt (AI), machine learning (ML), chat botlar, huquqiy prognozlash, huquqiy tadqiqotlar.

**IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN
LEGAL PRACTICE: THEORETICAL-LEGAL RESEARCH
ANNOTATION**

This article presents the concept of artificial intelligence (AI) and the scope of its application in legal practice. It explores international experiences with AI, discusses the challenges arising from its use, and proposes several solutions.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), chatbots, legal forecasting, legal research.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, where information technology has become an integral part of society, advances in technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) are being utilized to enhance both personal and professional activities. The changes taking place in the 21st century, often referred to as the "digital age" have a direct impact on the legal field. The rapid development of digital and information technologies necessitates changes in legal practices as well. New approaches to understanding legal technologies are emerging, and new categories are being developed to account for the impact of digitization on legal realities.

At present, while Uzbekistan is making effective use of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, there is an urgent need to establish a comprehensive legal framework for the field. This framework would define the limits of AI usage to ensure the protection of citizens' rights and freedoms. Currently, relations in the field of artificial intelligence in Uzbekistan are governed by five scattered normative legal documents. These documents outline the application of AI technologies in various sectors, including healthcare, education, the economy, social services, and public administration.

The adoption of a special decision by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021 has facilitated the systematization and organization of work in this area. Specifically, the "Program of Measures to Improve the Republic of Uzbekistan's Position in the Artificial Intelligence Readiness Index" was approved. The program places special emphasis on the development and use of AI technologies across economic sectors, the social sphere, and in the state

administration system. It also focuses on the integration of AI into key sectors such as agriculture, energy, healthcare, and e-government.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The use of AI in legal practice is being implemented on a large scale today. There are several advantages to employing this technology. Among them are intelligent virtual assistants that improve work efficiency, simplify tasks, and analyze large volumes of data. Legal professionals often deal with paper-based documents. Reviewing legal documents – from contracts to lawsuits – is a core aspect of legal practice. In this context, AI offers a solution by simplifying document automation processes and improving efficiency.

AI generally refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines designed to perform tasks that typically require human perception. In the legal sector, AI technologies are simplifying routine tasks like legal research, document review, and contract analysis. Additionally, AI can handle increasing workloads without a proportional increase in costs.

Key AI applications in legal practice include:

Document Review and Contract Analysis: AI-powered tools can analyze vast amounts of legal documents, identify relevant information, and extract key insights.

Legal Research: Natural Language Processing (NLP) allows machines to understand and interpret human language, enabling them to analyze and extract information from legal documents, contracts, and court rulings.

Predictive Analytics: Machine Learning (ML) algorithms can predict case outcomes and classify legal documents.

In September 2021, the International Bar Association published a report in which legal organizations from various countries shared insights on the practical

use of AI systems in their jurisdictions. Based on these findings, Tracy Calvert, president of Oakalls Consultancy, identified six areas where intelligent systems are involved:

- Automation of legal practice;
- Legal forecasting;
- Preparation of normative legal documents;
- Legal research and analysis;
- Legal consultation technologies;
- Chatbot systems for communication.

Currently, many countries are developing legal regulations to govern technologies that utilize AI. This is reflected in the rapid creation of new legal norms at the level of state bodies and interstate organizations across different regions. China has emerged as a leader in the legal regulation of AI, aiming to outpace other global political entities. At a minimum, three key areas are driving competition between states and their associations:

1. The level of AI development
2. The pace of its development
3. The level of legal regulation in this area

China consistently ranks second in AI development, primarily due to the influence of the United States. Since 2013, China has actively integrated Internet technologies into its judicial process, allowing court proceedings to be conducted online and supporting participants with AI-driven software. For example, the FaXiaotao program analyzes similar court cases based on given facts, organizes decisions, and calculates the probability of a successful outcome. Additionally, the program provides legal advice and helps clients find specialized lawyers at the early stages of the legal process. In some provinces, China uses the Mobile Micro Court software, which facilitates online document submission and remote court hearings. This reduces time and financial costs while limiting physical interaction – important

during pandemics or quarantine situations. However, virtual communication eliminates certain aspects of traditional court sessions, such as the presence and non-verbal behavior of witnesses.

While there are clear advantages to AI in the legal field, there are also legal challenges. A system trained to perceive and analyze external information can behave in ways its creators did not anticipate. Since AI systems often operate autonomously, it can be difficult to assign legal liability. Various forms of AI regulation already exist, such as copyright or intellectual property laws, but the autonomous actions of AI systems complicate the application of current regulations. For instance, current intellectual property (IP) laws do not address the possibility of AI acting independently of its developers or users. Some scholars suggest applying animal laws to AI, considering it as a form of property capable of autonomous action. National legislation generally treats AI under existing ownership rules (e.g, Article 93 of the Civil Code). However, this approach, especially in the context of liability, is limited. First, it is inappropriate to apply animal-related liability laws to robots under criminal law. Second, animal laws are typically designed for domesticated animals, which do not generally pose risks to their owners or others. For this reason, some experts advocate applying stricter regulations, similar to those used for the conservation of wild animals.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the role of AI in legal practice is undeniable and its future development is promising. As AI technology continues to evolve, its integration into legal workflows will deepen, providing more sophisticated tools for document automation and other aspects of legal practice. To balance the legal regulation of automation with societal safety, we must first address a number of challenges. AI raises questions in social, economic, political, technological, legal, ethical, and philosophical domains. To navigate the uncertainties, opportunities, and potential risks associated with AI, it is essential to understand the interconnectedness of these

areas. Continued scientific and practical research is vital for addressing the complex issues surrounding AI in legal practice.

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